

TASTE SENSITIVITY AND ITS ASSOCIATION WITH DIETARY INADEQUACY AMONG OLDER ADULTS: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Aging is associated with physiological changes that can impair taste sensitivity, potentially affecting dietary intake and overall nutritional status. This study, titled “Evaluation of Taste Sensitivity in Elder People and Its Association with Inadequate Dietary Intake,” aimed to assess how variations in taste perception influence nutrient consumption in elder individuals. A cross-sectional study was conducted among 70 participants aged 61 to 93 years. Taste sensitivity for sweet, salt, sour, and bitter were evaluated using graded concentrations, and dietary intake was assessed through a 3-day dietary recall and analyzed using DIETCAL software. Anthropometric indicators such as Body Mass Index (BMI), Mid-Upper Arm Circumference (MUAC), and calf circumference were used to assess nutritional status. The results showed that moderate taste sensitivity was most common for sweet, sour, and bitter tastes, while high sensitivity predominated for salt. Statistically significant associations were observed between sugar taste

sensitivity and vitamin B6 intake, salt taste sensitivity and phosphorous intake, and bitter taste sensitivity and ascorbic acid intake. While most other associations were not statistically significant, high rates of deficiency in zinc, calcium, iron, and magnesium were prevalent across all taste sensitivity groups, indicating potential nutritional vulnerabilities. The findings

highlight a complex relationship between taste perception and nutrient intake in elder individuals. Reduced taste sensitivity may limit food variety and contribute to nutrient deficiencies. Following the study, nutrition education was provided to promote healthy eating practices, emphasizing the use of natural flavor enhancers, colorful foods, and supportive strategies to enhance overall dietary intake and wellbeing.

KEYWORDS: Aging, taste sensitivity, dietary intake, nutritional status, healthy eating, natural flavors, wellbeing.

INTRODUCTION

Population aging is a global phenomenon, with individuals aged 60 years and above representing the fastest-growing demographic group worldwide. Although the proportional representation of older adults is lower in developing countries, these regions account for a substantial share of the global elderly population. In 1990, more than 250 million individuals aged ≥ 60 years resided in developing nations, comprising approximately 58% of the world's elderly population (Amarya et al., 2018). This demographic transition presents significant challenges to health systems, particularly with respect to nutrition and age-related functional decline.

Aging is biologically characterized by progressive morphofunctional involution affecting multiple physiological systems. Structural, functional, and molecular alterations occurring with advancing age impair organ function and homeostasis, thereby influencing nutritional status and overall health (Neumann et al., 2016). Among the various determinants of nutritional vulnerability in older adults, sensory decline—particularly impaired taste perception—plays a critical role.

Elderly individuals are at increased risk of malnutrition due to a complex interplay of physiological, psychological, and socioeconomic factors. Physiological contributors include reduced salivary secretion, dysphagia, gastrointestinal disorders, chronic illness, appetite loss, and sensory deterioration. Altered taste perception often leads to complaints of food blandness, which may negatively influence food preferences, appetite, and dietary intake, thereby increasing the risk of inadequate nutrient consumption (Methven et al., 2012).

Taste perception is a key determinant of food selection and eating behavior. Individuals with reduced taste sensitivity may require higher concentrations of tastants or increased food

intake to achieve comparable sensory perception, whereas individuals with greater sensitivity tend to consume smaller quantities of foods expressing specific taste qualities (Costanzo, 2024). Taste perception begins with the chemical activation of taste receptor cells by tastant molecules, resulting in neurotransmitter release and stimulation of gustatory nerve fibers. Taste buds, composed of specialized sensory cells, are primarily located on fungiform, foliate, and circumvallate papillae of the tongue (Cai *et al.*, 2014).

Five basic taste modalities—sweet, salty, sour, bitter, and umami—are detected through distinct receptor mechanisms. Sweet, bitter, and umami tastes are mediated by G protein-coupled receptors, namely T1Rs and T2Rs. Notably, these receptors are also expressed in extraoral tissues such as the gastrointestinal tract, respiratory system, brain, and reproductive organs, indicating broader physiological functions beyond gustation (Li, 2013).

Taste sensitivity declines with age, typically becoming evident after 60 years. This decline has been attributed to a reduction in the number and size of taste buds, alterations in neural processing, and age-related physiological changes. Polypharmacy, common among older adults, further contributes to taste disturbances, with approximately 11% of elderly individuals experiencing medication-induced taste alterations (Jeon *et al.*, 2021).

Aging also influences dietary patterns and nutrient intake. Older adults tend to consume smaller meals, eat more slowly, snack less frequently, and derive a higher proportion of energy from carbohydrates while consuming less fat. Despite a reduction in energy expenditure with age, energy intake often declines to a greater extent, predisposing elderly individuals to weight loss and nutrient deficiencies (Parker *et al.*, 2004). Micronutrient inadequacies, particularly zinc deficiency, are prevalent and have been associated with impaired immune function, delayed wound healing, appetite loss, and altered taste and smell perception (Pisano *et al.*, 2016).

Given the close relationship between taste sensitivity, dietary intake, and nutritional status, the present study aims to evaluate taste sensitivity among elderly individuals and to examine its association with inadequate dietary intake. The findings are expected to inform targeted nutritional interventions to enhance taste perception, improve dietary adequacy, and prevent malnutrition in older adults.

METHODOLOGY

An observational, cross-sectional study was conducted to evaluate taste sensitivity among elderly individuals and to examine its association with inadequate dietary intake. The study was carried out at the Lions Club Old Age Home, Dindigul, Tamil Nadu. A total of 70 elderly participants (men and women) aged ≥ 60 years were selected using a convenience sampling technique. Elderly individuals who were willing to participate were included in the study, while those with dementia, acute illness, oral lesions, fever, cold symptoms, or a history of gastrointestinal, neurological, head, neck, or ear surgeries were excluded.

Data collection was conducted over a period of one month, following ethical clearance and informed consent from all participants. Demographic information was collected using a structured questionnaire. Anthropometric measurements including height, weight, mid-upper arm circumference (MUAC), and calf circumference were recorded using standardized procedures. Height was measured using a calibrated portable stadiometer, and body weight was assessed using a validated weighing scale. Body mass index (BMI) was calculated as weight (kg)/height² (m²) and classified according to World Health Organization (WHO) criteria. MUAC and calf circumference were measured using a non-stretchable measuring tape and interpreted using WHO and Asian Working Group for Sarcopenia (AWGS) reference standards, respectively.

Taste sensitivity was assessed for the four basic tastes—sweet, salty, sour, and bitter—using aqueous solutions prepared in three graded concentrations for each taste. Participants were instructed to rinse their mouth with water before the test. Each solution was administered sequentially, and taste perception was scored on a standardized scale ranging from 0 (no taste perception) to 5 (very strong taste perception). Scores were recorded within one minute of tasting, and overall taste sensitivity was determined based on cumulative scores for each taste modality.

Dietary intake was assessed using a three-day dietary recall method, including two weekdays and one weekend day selected at random. Participants were interviewed to obtain detailed information on food consumption, portion sizes, and meal timing. Nutrient intake, including macronutrients and micronutrients, was calculated using DIETCAL software and compared with recommended dietary allowances to assess inadequacy.

Following data collection, nutrition education was provided to participants focusing on age-related changes in taste perception, the importance of adequate nutrient intake, and practical strategies to enhance food palatability using natural flavor enhancers. Educational pamphlets prepared in both Tamil and English were distributed to reinforce key messages.

Statistical analysis was performed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Data were expressed as mean and standard deviation. The association between taste sensitivity and inadequate dietary intake was analyzed using the Chi-square test. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULT

Table No. 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Study Population.

Variable	Mean \pm SD / n (%)
Age (years)	68.57 \pm 6.52
Male	28 (40.0)
Female	42 (60.0)

A total of 70 elderly participants aged ≥ 60 years were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 68.57 \pm 6.52 years, with ages ranging from 61 to 93 years. Females constituted a higher proportion of the study population (60%) compared to males (40%).

Table No. 2: Anthropometric characteristics of the participants.

Parameter	Mean \pm SD
Height (cm)	155.31 \pm 7.45
Weight (kg)	62.58 \pm 11.89
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.01 \pm 4.65
MUAC (cm)	29.53 \pm 3.94
Calf circumference (cm)	33.76 \pm 7.70

The mean height and weight of the participants were 155.31 \pm 7.45 cm and 62.58 \pm 11.89 kg, respectively. The mean BMI was 26.01 \pm 4.65 kg/m², indicating a predominance of overweight among the elderly population. Mean mid-upper arm circumference (MUAC) was 29.53 \pm 3.94 cm, suggesting generally normal nutritional status. The mean calf circumference was 33.76 \pm 7.70 cm, approaching the cut-off values for sarcopenia risk.

Table No. 3: Distribution of taste sensitivity among elderly participants.

Taste	Mild n (%)	Moderate n (%)	High n (%)
Sweet	30 (42.9)	35 (50.0)	5 (7.1)
Salt	–	21 (30.0)	49 (70.0)

Sour	9 (12.9)	43 (61.4)	18 (25.7)
Bitter	14 (20.0)	42 (60.0)	14 (20.0)

Moderate taste sensitivity was predominant across all taste modalities. High sensitivity was most frequently observed for salt (70%), whereas sugar sensitivity was largely moderate (50%). Bitter and sour tastes also showed a predominance of moderate sensitivity. Taste sensitivity assessment showed that moderate sensitivity was most common for all taste modalities, while salt sensitivity remained relatively preserved. This preservation of salt taste perception in elderly individuals has been reported earlier and may be attributed to dietary habituation and frequent salt exposure.

Table No. 4: Significant associations between taste sensitivity and nutrient intake.

Taste modality	Nutrient	p-value
Sweet	Vitamin B6	0.042*
Salt	Protein	0.033*
Salt	Phosphorus	0.026*
Bitter	Ascorbic acid	0.034*

Most macronutrient and micronutrient inadequacies were not significantly associated with taste sensitivity; however, a few specific and meaningful associations were identified. A statistically significant association was observed between sugar taste sensitivity and vitamin B6 intake ($p = 0.042$). In addition, salt taste sensitivity showed significant associations with protein intake ($p = 0.033$) and phosphorus intake ($p = 0.026$). Bitter taste sensitivity was also significantly associated with ascorbic acid intake ($p = 0.034$). These findings indicate that although overall taste sensitivity was not a dominant determinant of dietary adequacy, selective taste impairments may influence the intake of specific nutrients.

The association between reduced sugar sensitivity and vitamin B6 inadequacy suggests that diminished sweet taste perception may adversely affect the consumption of carbohydrate-rich foods that serve as important sources of B-complex vitamins. Similarly, the observed relationship between salt sensitivity and protein intake implies that alterations in salt taste perception may influence the intake of protein-rich savory foods. Furthermore, the significant association between bitter taste sensitivity and vitamin C intake may reflect the avoidance of bitter-tasting fruits and vegetables, leading to reduced ascorbic acid consumption among elderly individuals.

Notably, a high prevalence of deficiencies in B-complex vitamins, calcium, iron, magnesium, and vitamin C was observed across all taste sensitivity categories. This pattern suggests that inadequate dietary intake among older adults may be influenced not only by age-related taste impairment but also by additional factors such as reduced appetite, limited food variety, institutionalized meal patterns, polypharmacy, and physiological changes associated with aging.

These findings are consistent with previous studies (Jeon *et al.*, 2021; Methven *et al.*, 2012), which have documented age-related declines in taste sensitivity and their potential contribution to suboptimal nutrient intake. However, the absence of significant associations for most nutrients indicates that taste sensitivity alone does not fully account for dietary inadequacy in the elderly, highlighting the multifactorial nature of malnutrition in this population.

CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrates that taste sensitivity among elderly individuals shows selective associations with dietary intake rather than a uniform influence across all nutrients. Significant relationships were identified between sweet taste sensitivity and vitamin B6 intake, salt taste sensitivity and protein and phosphorus intake, and bitter taste sensitivity and ascorbic acid intake. These findings suggest that specific taste impairments may contribute to targeted nutrient inadequacies by influencing food preferences and consumption patterns in older adults.

Despite these associations, widespread deficiencies of several micronutrients—including B-complex vitamins, calcium, iron, magnesium, and vitamin C—were observed across all levels of taste sensitivity. This indicates that inadequate dietary intake in the elderly is multifactorial and cannot be attributed solely to age-related declines in taste perception. Factors such as reduced appetite, limited dietary variety, institutional food practices, polypharmacy, and physiological changes associated with aging are likely to play substantial roles.

The predominance of moderate taste sensitivity and the relative preservation of salt taste perception observed in this study align with previous research, reinforcing the notion that gustatory decline is selective rather than universal. Importantly, these findings highlight the need for comprehensive nutritional strategies that go beyond addressing sensory decline alone.

Targeted nutrition education emphasizing the use of natural flavor enhancers, increased dietary variety, and nutrient-dense foods may help mitigate taste-related barriers to adequate intake. Future research employing larger sample sizes, longitudinal designs, and objective taste threshold measurements is warranted to further elucidate causal relationships and to inform the development of tailored nutritional interventions aimed at preventing malnutrition and promoting healthy aging.

REFERENCE

1. Peel, N., Bartlett, H. and McClure, R., 2004. Healthy ageing: how is it defined and measured?. *Australasian Journal on Ageing*, 23(3): 115-119.
2. Methven, L., Allen, V.J., Withers, C.A. and Gosney, M.A., 2012. Ageing and taste. *Proceedings of the nutrition society*, 71(4): 556-565.
3. Costanzo, A., 2024. Temporal patterns in taste sensitivity. *Nutrition reviews*, 82(6): 831- 847.
4. Cai, H., Maudsley, S. and Martin, B., 2014. Taste Buds of the Tongue. How gut and brain control metabolism, 42: 134-146.
5. Jeon, S., Kim, Y., Min, S., Song, M., Son, S. and Lee, S., 2021. Taste sensitivity of elderly people is associated with quality of life and inadequate dietary intake. *Nutrients*, 13(5): 1693.
6. Pisano, M. and Hilar, O., 2016. Zinc and taste disturbances in older adults: a review of the literature. *The Consultant Pharmacist*, 31(5): 267-270.
7. Barragán, R., Coltell, O., Portolés, O., Asensio, E.M., Sorlí, J.V., Ortega-Azorín, C., González, J.I., Sáiz, C., Fernández-Carrión, R., Ordovas, J.M. and Corella, D., 2018. Bitter, sweet, salty, sour and umami taste perception decreases with age: sex-specific analysis, modulation by genetic variants and taste-preference associations in 18- to 80-year-old subjects. *Nutrients*, 10(10): 1539.
8. Delilbasi, C., Cehiz, T., Akal, U. and Yilmaz, T., 2003. Evaluation of some factors affecting taste perception in elderly people. *Oral Health and Dental Management in the Black Sea Countries*, 4(6): 29-35.
9. Sergi, G., Bano, G., Pizzato, S., Veronese, N. and Manzato, E., 2017. Taste loss in the elderly: Possible implications for dietary habits. *Critical reviews in food science and nutrition*, 57(17): 3684-3689.
10. Liu, F., Yin, J., Wang, J. and Xu, X., 2022. Food for the elderly based on sensory perception: A review. *Current Research in Food Science*, 5: 1550-1558.

11. Farapti, F., Putri, S.A., Furqonia, A.W., Rejeki, P.S. and Miftahussurur, M., 2024. High Potassium Diet Rich in Spices and Herbs-Salt Substitution (HPSH-SS) for Blood Pressure Reduction in Older Adults: Protocol for Diet Concept and Randomized Controlled Trial. *JMIR Research Protocols*, 13(1): e56869.
12. Wilson, M.M.G., Thomas, D.R., Rubenstein, L.Z., Chibnall, J.T., Anderson, S., Baxi, A., Diebold, M.R. and Morley, J.E., 2005. Appetite assessment: simple appetite questionnaire predicts weight loss in community-dwelling adults and nursing home residents. *The American journal of clinical nutrition*, 82(5): 1074-1081.
13. Neumann, L., Schauren, B.C. and Adami, F.S., 2016. Taste sensitivity of adults and elderly persons. *Revista Brasileira de Geriatria e Gerontologia*, 19: 797-808.
14. Ng, K., Woo, J., Kwan, M., Sea, M., Wang, A., Lo, R., Chan, A. and Henry, C.J.K., 2004. Effect of age and disease on taste perception. *Journal of pain and symptom management*, 28(1): 28-34.
15. Toffanello, E.D., Inelmen, E.M., Imoscopi, A., Perissinotto, E., Coin, A., Miotto, F., Donini, L.M., Cucinotta, D., Barbagallo, M., Manzato, E. and Sergi, G., 2013. Taste loss in hospitalized multimorbid elderly subjects. *Clinical interventions in aging*, 167-174.